

Wisdom and Humor in a Village of Birds
Amazon Book Review Series of “Wild Wise Weird”

Kateryna Malai

United States, December 28, 2024

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With Kingfisher as our smart and charming narrator, this anthology of fables is a fascinating medley of cultural charm, wit, and wisdom. Set against a colorful Vietnamese backdrop, each story combines humorous societal commentary with timeless life lessons. I was entertained and inspired by this thought-provoking and engrossing read.

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★★★★★ **I Found Wisdom and Humor in a Village of Birds**

Reviewed in the United States on December 28, 2024

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Screenshot. Review of “Wild Wise Weird” by Malai [1]. Reviewed in the United States on December 28, 2024.

(*) Note: This paper reprints of Malai’s review [1] appearing on the Amazon page of the title [2]. The reprint’s title is created based on the review’s content.

References

[1] Malai, K. (2024, Dec. 28). I Found Wisdom and Humor in a Village of Birds. <https://www.amazon.com/gp/customer-reviews/R30DPE434HVGBM/>

[2] Vuong, Q. H. (2024). *Wild Wise Weird*. <https://www.amazon.com/dp/B0BG2NNHY6/>